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THE ROLE OF DIDACTIC PRINCIPLES IN MODULAR-CREDIT LEARNING

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Abstract: In the system of modern higher education, the entire structure is being modernized, with the emphasis shifting to the interests of students in line with the humanistic traditions of pedagogy. This is the key feature underlying the introduction of the module-credit learning system. Didactic principles aim to enhance the effectiveness of knowledge acquisition in a short period, taking into account the specific features and requirements of modular learning. Overall, the focus on the formation and graduation of a professionally competent specialist who is in demand in the labor market signifies a reform and restructuring of the educational process. It is transformed from a passive process of knowledge assimilation into an active one, emphasizing the development of skills for practical application in professional life.

Key words: knowledge, pedagogical principles, didactics, modular training, credits, humanistic principles of education.

Annotatsiya: Zamonaviy oliy ta'lim tizimida hozirgi kunda butun tizim modernizatsiya qilinmoqda, asosiy e'tibor pedagogikaning gumanistik yo'nalishi an'alarida talabaning manfaatlariga qaratilmoqda. Bu modulli-kreditli ta'limni joriy etish mazmunining asosiy xususiyatidir. Didaktik tamoyillar modulli ta'limning xususiyatlari va talablari asosida bilimlarni qisqa muddatda samarali o'zlashtirishga xizmat qiladi. Umuman olganda, mehnat bozorida talab yuqori bo'lgan, kasbiy jihatdan malakali mutaxassisni shakllantirish va yetishtirishga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv ta'lim jarayonini isloh qilish va qayta tashkil etishni anglatadi. Bu jarayon bilimlarni passiv o'zlashtirishdan ularni kasbiy faoliyatda qo'llash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga yo'naltirilgan faol jarayonga aylanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: bilim, pedagogik tamoyillar, didaktika, modulli ta'lim, kreditlar, gumanistik ta'lim tamoyillari.

Аннотация: В системе современного высшего образования в настоящее время модернизируется вся структура, акцент смещается на интересы студента в традициях гуманистического направления педагогики. В этом заключается ключевая особенность смысла внедрения модульно-кредитного обучения. Дидактические принципы призваны повысить эффективность усвоения знаний в краткие сроки с учётом особенностей и требований модульного обучения. В целом ориентация на формирование и выпуск профессионально компетентного специалиста, востребованного на рынке труда, означает реформирование и перестройку образовательного процесса, который трансформируется из пассивного усвоения знаний в активный процесс с формированием навыков их практического применения в профессиональной жизни.

Ключевые слова: знание, педагогические принципы, дидактика, модульное обучение, кредиты, гуманистические принципы образования.

INTRODUCTION

In Uzbekistan's higher education system, credit-modular and modular-rating teaching technologies are being actively implemented to comprehensively modernize traditional pedagogical practices. Modular technology in didactic processes involves structuring educational content into independent organizational and methodological units—modules. The composition and scope of these modules vary based on students' academic profiles, levels, and learning objectives. This method enables students to personalize their learning pathways. By modularizing disciplines, key concepts can be systematically grouped and logically integrated into a cohesive knowledge framework, minimizing redundancy and forming a structured content module.

Higher education didactics, a rapidly evolving field within pedagogical science, explores teaching and learning processes at the tertiary level. The growing demand for research in this area is driven by the adoption of modular-credit education and the challenges facing modern universities. Researchers focus on optimizing didactic strategies, identifying patterns in the learning process, advancing higher education theories, refining educational technologies, and enhancing pedagogical tools to improve teaching effectiveness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The analysis of scientific research and publications reveals that various aspects of organizing students' independent work have been explored by scholars such as I. Lerner, L. Derkach, and V. Kazakov, among others. In the field of higher education didactics and methodology, numerous studies have addressed the challenges of structuring independent student work, including those by A. Alexyuk and V. P. Pidkasistoy. The motivation behind students' learning activities has been examined by researchers like V. Aksenova, T. Gusak, V. Krylova, and V. Leontiev, while methods for improving students' preparation for independent learning have been analyzed by M. Antoniuk, N. Vazheevskaya, and I. Soldatenko. Additionally, the modular training system has been comprehensively studied by A. Oleksiuk and A. Humeniuk.

In his research, Y. K. Babansky emphasized optimizing the learning process through modules, while V. P. Bepalko regarded it as an essential mechanism for managing learning activities. S. I. Kulikov focused on integrating various teaching methods and approaches, and V. B. Zakoryukin explored the flexibility of constructing educational content from modular units. Building on these theoretical foundations, educators have highlighted the role of cognitive activity in shaping the learning process, as emphasized by P. Ya. Galperin. A key insight from this theory is that action serves as the central element in managing the cognitive development process. Soviet pedagogical perspectives view learning as a managed process that balances teacher-led instruction with student self-regulation. Collaboration between educators and students is seen as essential for achieving successful outcomes. According to S. I. Arkhangelsky, in modular learning, the teacher plays the highest role in the hierarchy of academic management, overseeing and structuring the core learning activities.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this study is grounded in a comparative analysis of scientific perspectives on the application of didactic techniques in modular-credit teaching, particularly in relation to their impact on learning and personal development. The research employs various methods, including literature selection and analysis, clarification of key terminology, general theoretical approaches, analogy, classification, and systematization. A methodological framework was utilized to examine the influence of didactic principles on education within the modular-credit learning system.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The modernization of higher education is currently a key focus, with an emphasis on student-centered learning aligned with humanistic pedagogical principles. This shift underpins the adoption of modular-credit training, which transforms traditional education from passive knowledge acquisition into an active process, equipping students with practical skills for their professional careers. The goal is to develop highly competent, market-ready specialists by restructuring the educational process.

A fundamental measure of a modern specialist's qualification is professional literacy, encompassing both substantive and procedural aspects of professional competence. Unlike the broad societal expectation of specialist training, professional competence reflects an individual's actual level of preparedness, necessitating continuous knowledge renewal and adaptation to evolving professional demands. The modular-credit system facilitates this by aligning with pedagogical didactic principles.

Currently, higher education institutions are actively implementing the modular-credit system. This approach personalizes learning, making it more aligned with humanistic pedagogy than traditional methods. The theory of modular-credit training is based on specific principles closely linked to general didactic foundations, defining its objectives, content, and instructional methods. The teacher's role shifts from a lecturer to a facilitator, while students move from passive recipients to active participants in discussions and learning activities. Each module concludes with an intermediate assessment, serving as a crucial checkpoint for both students and instructors.

Analyzing various educational quality improvement efforts reveals key principles for effective learning: consciousness and engagement, visualization, systematicity, sustainability, scientific validity, accessibility, and the integration of theory with practice. Among these, the didactic principle of consciousness and activity is particularly significant for modular-credit education. This principle is founded on the idea that deep, independent comprehension of knowledge is achieved through active cognitive engagement. Factors such as learning motivation, cognitive activity levels, instructional organization, and teaching methods influence students' conscious assimilation of knowledge.

Empirical observations confirm that fostering conscious engagement enhances learning effectiveness. A step-by-step modular study approach facilitates mastery of subjects, while modular learning technologies manage the educational process in line with specialization requirements. This structured approach minimizes the challenges young specialists face when integrating into professional environments.

Modular structures are designed as coherent educational systems aligned with specific professional competencies. They transfer course content into structured modules, ensuring logical progression and content integrity. In Uzbekistan, the modular-credit system has been piloted in universities, with ongoing evaluations to refine its implementation. It is gradually being integrated into the national higher education framework to ensure continuous educational improvement.

The modular – credit training theory is based on core pedagogical principles, including:

- **Independence** – Encouraging student autonomy in learning.
- **Modularity** – Structuring content into self-contained learning units.
- **Conscious perspective** – Fostering a goal-oriented approach to education.
- **Dynamism** – Adapting educational content to societal and technological advancements.
- **Isolation of key elements** – Ensuring focused learning within each module.

The principle of modularity structures learning into distinct functional units designed to achieve specific educational objectives. The principle of isolating key elements ensures that educational material is presented as a cohesive unit tailored to particular didactic goals. Meanwhile, dynamism allows for the continuous refinement of modules to align with societal and technological needs.

The effectiveness of education depends on aligning learning content with students' capabilities. The absence of practical application within training can hinder professional readiness. Additionally, a lack of pedagogical skills, ineffective use of teaching methods, and inappropriate selection of instructional strategies can prevent the achievement of didactic objectives.

The principle of parity emphasizes a consultative, student-centered approach, promoting independent learning while maintaining structured guidance. Pedagogical principles in modular learning are interdependent, shaping both content and instructional methodologies. Their alignment with general didactic principles reinforces the necessity of continual educational transformation. Transitioning to a modular-credit system requires assessing institutional readiness to ensure that educational reforms elevate learning outcomes to a new level.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

All pedagogical principles of modular training are closely interrelated and carry a functional load. They (in addition to the principle of parity) determine the design features of the content that emerge during the implementation of the modular approach in the learning process. All the aforementioned principles are based on general didactic principles and are interrelated with them. For the practical realization of the principle of consciousness and activity in learning, it is necessary to implement it within the educational process under the module-credit system as one of the most effective approaches. In this case, the rules of learning should be observed: clearly understand the goals and objectives of the upcoming work – explain to students the importance and significance of the topic and disclose the perspectives; teach in such a way that the student understands what, why, and how to do something, and never performs training actions mechanically without first deeply realizing their purpose; what is unknown to the learner should be logically linked to what is already known: where there is no logical connection between the new and existing knowledge, conscious learning does not occur; students should be placed in situations that require them to identify and explain discrepancies between observed facts and existing knowledge; when designing a lesson, it should be remembered that learning will be more successful if each rule is accompanied by examples, ensuring the variety of applications is sufficiently clear.

Module-based learning, when designed with pedagogical patterns in mind, leads to multiple positive effects that help achieve didactic goals: a student using didactic materials and instructions gains greater independence in mastering the subject; the teacher's role shifts from lecturer to consultant; the student's passive perception of material decreases, enabling active discussion with the teacher and fostering cognitive needs; intermediate control points align with the end of each module, which is beneficial for both students and teachers; it allows step-by-step learning of complete modules, facilitated by pedagogical patterns for easier mastery of the entire subject.

The advantages of implementing a modular credit system include a high degree of academic freedom, an independent nature of training, a developing style of cognitive activity, innovative content in educational programs, expanded university components within educational programs, an increase in problem-stimulating and interactive teaching methods, a predominance of practical forms of instruction, systematic and step-by-step control of students' academic work, productive and research-based levels of knowledge acquisition, and compatibility with any national educational system. Consequently, it can be concluded that as a result of

applying modular technology based on pedagogical principles, students develop fundamental characteristics that help them become increasingly independent and self-governing individuals. Their motivation to succeed, as well as their willingness to learn, is driven by the desire to solve professional and personal problems and to achieve specific goals through educational activities.

Didactic principles are universal across all subjects and levels of pedagogical work. A positive effect in the education and training of students can be achieved if the system of didactic principles is observed. An analysis of pedagogical literature shows that didactic principles are not static or unchangeable. With the development of pedagogical science, the accumulation of experience, and social progress, these principles evolve and improve. Throughout the history of pedagogical science, didactic principles have undergone significant changes in response to shifting socio-economic conditions, societal needs, and the educational goals for younger generations.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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